

Unfitted Finite Element Methods: a modern paradigm for advanced numerical simulations

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Introduction

Enriched and unfitted finite element methods are powerful extensions of the popular classical Finite Element Method (FEM). In FEM, piecewise polynomial functions defined over geometrically simple elements are used to represent both the geometry of the computational domain and the solution of the boundary value problem of interest. Over the years, researchers have identified limitations to this framework.

- (i) Meshing complex domains may be difficult, numerically costly and may lack robustness;
- (ii) Adaptive modeling requires numerous re-meshing operations during the solution process in order to improve the accuracy and/or stability of the numerical simulation. These re-meshing cycles can be computationally expensive and should be avoided;
- (iii) FE solvers for boundary value problems whose solutions exhibit singularities or discontinuities are slow to converge with mesh refinement. This is particularly true for higher-order methods, where sharp solution features may trigger instabilities.

Unfitted and enriched FEMs, such as the Partition-of-Unity FEM [Babuška-1997], eXtended FEM (XFEM) [Belytschko-1999], Generalised FEM [Strouboulis-2001], the Strong Discontinuity Approach [Oliver-2002] or the Finite Cell Method [Parvizian-2007], enhance the description of the geometry and solution field to circumvent some or all of these limitations. In this paper, we showcase one particular family of unfitted FEMs that is derived from the CutFEM method

Figure 1: Two particles enclosed in a rectangular domain. To represent jumps and kinks of the solution across the interfaces between different materials, intersected elements are doubled or tripled. The blue shaded element contains part of all three domains. It is tripled, whilst the yellow shaded elements are doubled.

[Hansbo-2002, Burman-2015]. Through a concise demonstration of its capabilities, we will highlight the fundamental algorithmic elements that distinguish unfitted and enriched FEM methods from the classical FEM.

I. Construction of enriched approximation spaces

Figure 2: Result of a 2D linear elastic computation over the domain depicted in Figure 1. Each subdomain has a different Young's modulus. Both the "out-of-plane" mesh deformation and the color map represent the magnitude of the FE displacement field. We can clearly see that the enriched FE space enables us to represent a triple kink inside an element. The integration on the cells containing interface parts is achieved by generating quadrature rules through sub-triangulation.

An important application of unfitted and enriched FEM technologies is represented in Figure 1 and 2. We propose to solve the equations of linearised elasticity over three perfectly bonded domains possessing different elasticity modulus. Due to this discontinuity in the field of material properties, the gradient of the exact solution field is expected to jump at the interface between domains. For the classical FEM, such jumps can only occur across edges between elements. Therefore, the mesh has to conform to the geometry: edges of the mesh need to align with the material interfaces. Unfitted FEMs alleviate the need for mesh conformity by allowing the numerical solution to jump or kink across interfaces that are embedded within the elements. In the context of the "CutFEM" method for example, such an enrichment of the FE solution space is obtained by (i) doubling/tripling the elements that are cut by the interface (Figure 1 and 2), and (ii) constraining the degrees of freedom of the cut elements in such a way that the perfect bonding conditions are satisfied across the embedded interface. Alternatively, the XFEM method enables us to represent non-conforming discontinuities by making use of the Partition-of-Unity Method.

Generally speaking, enriched FEMs find applications in fields wherever solution fields are known to exhibit sharp features that are not well captured by a piecewise polynomial FE space. Beside unfitted FEMs, an important class of enriched FEMs is dedicated to the efficient numerical solution of singular problems. In this context, the Partition-of-Unity Method is a popular way to allow singularities of known shape and order to be represented exactly within an enriched FE space.

II. Advanced applications

Contact between micro-components

in a composite material. Figure 3 and 4 show the longitudinal stress component in a 3D braided reinforced composite material undergoing uniaxial tension. All the subcomponents of the composite are modelled as isotropic, with an elastic contrast between fibres and matrix set to 10. Such a large ratio generates significant stress jumps between components. The problem is solved using an unfitted FEM. The computational mesh is a

Figure 3: stress component in a 3D braided reinforced composite material undergoing uniaxial tension. The multi-material elasticity problem is solved over a background regular mesh, using a dedicated unfitted FEM.

regular tessellation of the matrix. Fibre-fibre and matrix-fibre interfaces cut through this grid. We enrich the approximation space using the “standard “CutFEM” approach as depicted in Figure 1, which allows the stress field to jump between subcomponents. The continuity of the displacement field over the unfitted interfaces is ensured iteratively using a tailored LaTin domain decomposition solver [Ladeveze-1999, Kerfriden-2009]. We can show that the solution converges optimally, meaning that the embedded interface does not affect the approximation properties of the FE solver.

Figure 4: Elasticity problem with unilateral contact conditions over embedded interfaces.

The CutFEM/LaTin solver can be easily extended to handle more complex, nonlinear interface conditions over non-conforming interfaces. In this instance, we replace the perfect bonding of all of the embedded interfaces of the composite by unilateral contact (the interface displacement field can jump in the tangential direction, and in the normal direction if the normal component of the traction vector is positive). The numerical results clearly show a separation of the micro-components, as seen in Figure 4. The appeal of the LaTin-based coupling lies in the fact that all the advanced unfitted FEM operations developed and tested for perfect bonding can be reused without modification to simulate unilateral contact.

Figure 5: Background mesh of dragon shell example. The time dependent sinus displacement (right) is applied to the tail region (elements marked in red (left)).

Partial differential equations (PDEs) over manifolds. In addition to representing sharp features inside elements, unfitted FEMs can also be employed to solve PDEs over manifolds. In Figure 5 and 6, we show the application of the CutFEM method to an embedded dragon shaped shell in transient elastodynamics. The shell midplane is embedded in a 3D regular background grid. A key point here is to use an appropriate stabilisation method to ensure that the system matrix is well conditioned. We encourage the dragon to fly by applying a time dependent harmonic displacement field to its tail (red colored elements in Figure 5). Figure 6 displays four snapshots of the flying motion of the dragon at the times indicated as red dots in Figure 5.

Figure 6: Flying motion of embedded dragon shell at 4 time snap shots.

III. Common numerical challenges in Enriched and Unfitted FEMs

Constraints over unfitted interfaces. Enforcing boundary or interface conditions over embedded geometries is not straightforward. For example, the numerical results of Figure 2 were obtained by enforcing that the displacement jump vanishes over the embedded interface (*i.e.* perfect bonding). This cannot be done at the algebraic level directly. Modern approaches perform these types of operations by employing Lagrange multiplier or penalty terms to the weak form. In the specific case of CutFEM, a consistent penalty regularisation approach, the Nitsche method, is systematically employed. All the results reported in this article have been obtained using a dedicated LaTIn solver for embedded interfaces, which is well suited to handle complex interface conditions such as unilateral contact.

Numerical Integration. Integration within cut or enriched elements needs to be carefully tailored. Indeed, cut elements may have complicated geometries, which prohibits the use of standard integration rules. In addition, the integration of sharp enrichment functions such as singularities requires specialist integration rules. In the context of the composite example presented in section II, we have used the simplest and most commonly applied solution, which is to subdivide each of the subdomains into triangles/tetrahedrons and perform a standard numerical quadrature (clearly visible in Figure 4).

Regularisation. A key challenge related to unfitted and enriched FEMs is to control the condition number of the resulting algebraic system of equations. This is because cutting may result in degrees of freedom being free to move without numerical control. As a consequence, algebraic solvers may perform poorly. The first way to tackle this problem is to regularise the weak formulation of the problem. The second approach is to develop appropriate preconditioners at the linear algebra level. The unfitted method that we showcase in this paper uses the former approach, as described in [Burman-2015].

Geometrical descriptors. Geometrical information in classical FEM is directly encoded within the position of the nodes of the FE mesh. For unfitted FEMs, the description of the geometry is independent of the mesh. For this purpose, *e.g.* parametrised curves, splines, NURBS or level set functions can be used. In this contribution, we use the level set method, in which the zero isoline of a scalar function describes the interface location.

Conclusion

Unfitted and Enriched FEMs are a powerful and now mature class of methods that have been used to solve a variety of complex problems in solid mechanics, fluid mechanics and electromagnetism. Their development has helped scientists to better understand the FEM by extending it far beyond what it was originally designed for. Today, these methods are mainly used in academia as they require a certain level of expertise in mixed formulations and stabilisation, which is not yet mainstream in the wider community of computational engineering. Incidentally, specialists of remeshing techniques have also made tremendous progress over the last twenty years. The choice between unfitted and fitted methods remains down to personal preference, and to a lesser extent, to the problem at hand.

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